

GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA – THE BIG PICTURE

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Abstract

The purpose of this report is to document some basic demographic statistics on Eastern Orthodox and Greek Orthodox in Australia. This report relies upon the Census statistics as the most accurate measure of religion, where religion is defined as the answer to the optional question “What is the person’s religion?”.

Keywords

Greek Orthodox, Eastern Orthodox, Christians, Australia, census,

INTRODUCTION

This report is in three parts. It proceeds from a macro-perspective on religion in the population to a more specific meso-outline of Eastern Orthodox in Australia and finally a micro-analysis of Greek Orthodox.

In Part 1, the analysis first considers the role of religion and Christianity in the Australian population as revealed by the Census and answers some basic questions such as:

- What is the general religious background of Australia?
- Has Christianity declined in Australia?
- Has the Christian background of Australia changed?

Part 2 of this report focuses on the numbers of Eastern Orthodox in Australia and it goes on to consider issues such as:

- Who are the Eastern Orthodox?
- How many Eastern Orthodox are there in Australia?
- What is the proportion of Eastern Orthodox in the Australian population?
- How have the numbers of Orthodox changed over the years?
- How do the numbers of Greek Orthodox compare against other faiths?

Part 3 concludes the analysis with a description of some features of the Greek orthodox population in Australia. It answers questions such as:

- How many people are Greek Orthodox?
- How are the distributed in terms of sex, age, place of birth, or area of residence?

PART 1 – RELIGION AND CHRISTIANITY IN AUSTRALIA

What is the general religious background of Australia?

Australia still remains a religious nation in the majority, with around 60% (all percentages rounded) professing some faith see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Overall religious affiliation in Australia – 2016.

The proportion of the category Christians (in which Eastern Orthodoxy is included), however, is now only around 52%. Around 39% of Australians indicate a secular response or no religion and there were 9% whose religion was inadequately stated.

Figure 2. Christians compared to the total population in Australia 1911-2016.

Has Christianity declined in Australia?

The proportion of Christians in Australia has declined considerably from 1954 to 2016 (see Figure 2).

Has the Christian background of Australia changed?

The Christian background has changed markedly since 1911. At that time 42% of all Christians were Anglican and 26% were Roman Catholic. Moving forward to 2016, the position is almost reversed with only 25% Anglican and 43% Roman Catholic. The overall pattern is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Pattern of Anglican and Roman Catholic affiliation in Australia 1911 – 2016

The demise of the Anglican Church has altered the religious landscape of Australia. Secondly, the ascendancy of Roman Catholics in the population of Christians, means that to all intents and purposes Australia in terms of Christianity can be viewed as more of a Roman Catholic nation. A third point from Figure 3 is the recent decline in the numbers of both these groups from 2011-2016. Given the increase in the overall Australian population this may reflect disaffection with these two major denominations. The recent decline is mirrored in the number of Eastern Orthodox but it may not be the case that the causes of the decline are similar.

Figure 4. Major Christian groups in Australia including Eastern Orthodox

Figure 4 shows an analysis of the major Christian groups in Australia. Only Christians not formally defined (nfd) have shown some increase but these represent a very small proportion of Christians overall.

PART 2 – EASTERN ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA

Who are the Eastern Orthodox?

The group called Eastern Orthodox in the Census is not homogeneous. It does include denominations that are part of the Episcopal Assembly of Oceania (Antiochian Orthodox, Greek Orthodox, Romanian Orthodox, Serbian Orthodox, Russian Orthodox Church Outside Russia). In addition, the Australian Bureau of Statistics adds Macedonian Orthodox and Albanian Orthodox plus some who are not classified elsewhere.

How many Eastern Orthodox are there in Australia?

There are 502,801 Eastern Orthodox in Australia. This broad classification of Eastern Orthodox is dominated by Greek Orthodox who comprise 74% of the Eastern Orthodox.

Eastern Orthodox according to the census includes: 373,591 Greek Orthodox, 41,019 Serbian Orthodox, 49,682 Macedonian Orthodox, 21,967 Russian Orthodox, 9,840 Antiochian Orthodox and 2,741 Ukrainian Orthodox plus other smaller groups (see Figure 5).

Figure 5. Proportion of Eastern Orthodox in the Australian population

What is the proportion of Eastern Orthodox in the Australian population?

At the present time the proportion of Orthodox in the Australian population is 2.15%. Figure 5 shows that the proportion has declined noticeably in the last Census and for the first time in many years is below 2.5%.

Figure 6. Census figures for Eastern Orthodox 1911-2016.

How have the numbers of Eastern Orthodox changed over the years?

The numbers of Orthodox have changed, firstly increasing at a steep rate since the 1950s then with slower growth and a recent decline (Figure 6). These reflect the influence of migration, birth rates and the aging of the population.

In the case of Eastern Orthodox, it is heavily weighted towards those who are over 65 years. This may reflect the pattern of adult migrations following World War II. For ages 35-54 there is also a bulge in the distribution of Eastern Orthodox.

Overall, the population of Eastern Orthodox is weighted (a) towards the middle-aged with (b) quite a high proportion of seniors and (c) only 38% under 34 years compared with 46% for the general Australian population (see Figure 7 for a side-by-side comparison of proportions).

Figure 7. Proportion in each age group – Australian population and Eastern Orthodox.

How do the numbers of Eastern Orthodox compare against non-Christian faiths?

In this section the numbers of Eastern Orthodox are compared to non-Christian faiths.

Figure 8. A comparison of Eastern Orthodox with Judaism and Islam in Australia 1976-2016.

Figure 8 compares Eastern Orthodoxy with Judaism and Islam. Since 1976 there has been a substantial increase in the number and proportion of Islam compared with Eastern Orthodox and

Judaism has shown a slight increase in numbers but not necessarily in its proportion.

Figure 9 compares Eastern Orthodoxy with Buddhism and Hindu in Australia. Since 1976, there has been a substantial increase in the number and proportion of Buddhists and Hindus in Australia compared with Eastern Orthodox. This also reflects changes in migration and the multicultural nature of Australia.

Figure 9. A comparison of Eastern Orthodoxy with Hindu and Buddhism in Australia 1976-2016.

PART 3 – GREEK ORTHODOX IN AUSTRALIA

This third section in the analysis deals solely with Greek Orthodox. In 2016, there was a finer breakdown of the figures for Eastern Orthodox and some characteristics of the Greek Orthodox population are defined in terms of age, residence, year of arrival.

How many people are Greek Orthodox?

In 2016, there were 373,591 Greek Orthodox throughout Australia, making up 1.59% of the population.

Greek Orthodox were categorised originally under the heading of Greek Catholic in the census and in recent times are included under the heading of Eastern Orthodox.

Male-Female. There were almost equal numbers of male and female Greek Orthodox in Australia (male = 184,395; female = 189,187).

Age. The age distribution of Greek Orthodox highlights the aging of the population in Australia, in that majority of Greek Orthodox are aged 45 years and over.

Figure 10 compares the proportion in each group for Greek Orthodox with that in the general population. It highlights much lower proportions of Greek Orthodox in the 0-4 years and 20-39 years groups. There are significantly higher proportions for the 70-74, 75-79, 80-84 and 85+ years age groups. Long-term there will be a demographic effect of the reduced numbers of 0-4 years and 20-39 years.

Figure 10. Greek Orthodox and the total population – a comparison of proportions by age group (years).

Place of Birth. Almost two-thirds of Greek Orthodox were born in Australia (63%) with some 29% born in Southern or Eastern Europe.

The year of arrival of those Greek Orthodox not born in Australia confirms that most arrived in the period 1956-1975 (see Figure 11).

Figure 11. Year of arrival of Greek Orthodox not born in Australia.

Area of residence. Just over 290,000 of the 373,591 Greek Orthodox reside in Victoria (44%) and New South Wales (34%). The distribution is depicted in Figure 12.

Most Greek Orthodox (92%) reside in metropolitan areas rather than non-urban or rural areas (see Figure 13), with 117,032 in Greater Sydney and 156,247 in Greater Melbourne. It is only in Queensland where the figure drops to 66% in the capital city area.

Figure 12. Greek orthodox by State or Territory.

Figure 13. Greek Orthodox by capital city area.

SUMMARY

In summary it can be said that Australia is still a religious nation with around 60% professing some faith but it is more heterogeneous than in the past.

It was once a predominantly Christian nation. Christians, however, have now declined to just over half of the population. It is likely that the proportion of Christians will decline further as their actual number in the population was reduced for the first time since 1911 in the last Census.

There have also been changes within Christianity as a whole. The Christian background has moved from being predominantly Anglican and Protestant to being Roman Catholic. In terms of Christianity, Australia can be viewed as a Roman Catholic nation because Catholics now comprise 43% of Christians. The other change in Christianity in Australia is the rise of the Orthodox faith, which ranks around equal fourth with Presbyterians.

The group called the Eastern Orthodox includes various denominations. Altogether there are just over 500,000 Eastern Orthodox in Australia and Greek Orthodox comprise almost three quarters.

For the first time in the history of the Census, the proportion of Eastern Orthodox in the Australian population has declined

together with the numbers of Eastern Orthodox. Part of the reason for this decline is demographic. It reflects the older age structure the Orthodox population, no large-scale migration and probably fertility rates.

Eastern Orthodoxy have also declined in terms of their position amongst all religions in Australia. Groups such as Islam and Hindu have overtaken Eastern Orthodoxy.

Altogether there are only 373,591 Greek Orthodox in Australia and they make up 1.59% of the population. This is much less than figures cited elsewhere such as “650000 Faithfull” (Tamis, 2009). The nature of the Greek Orthodox population is characterised by:

- almost equal numbers of male and female;
- an aging population with most Greek Orthodox aged 45 years and over;
- a touch under two-thirds of the Greek Orthodox (63%) were born in Australia;
- of those who were not born in Australia, most arrived in the period 1956 to 1975;
- 78% of Greek Orthodox resign in Victoria and New South Wales;
- most Greek Orthodox reside in metropolitan areas with 117000 in Sydney and 156000 in greater Melbourne.

These statistics will confirm some views but also challenge some misconceptions about the numbers of Orthodox. Certainly, the findings could have implications for the planning of Greek Orthodox religious, health, education or welfare services.

No doubt the findings will be interpreted in a number of different ways but there is no predetermined criteria for their application. What can be said, however, is that (a) the numbers of Greek Orthodox are declining; (b) the overall position of Greek Orthodoxy in the religious landscape of Australia is fairly constant within the Christian of denominations; but (c) its position is moving lower across all faiths when non-Christian religions are included.

The results of the findings provide opportunities for implementation. Future papers in this series will undertake more detailed comparisons as well as finer analyses of Greek Orthodox in Australia.

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